

GRAMMATICAL CONTENT OF PERSON'S AGE CATEGORY

*Sh. Ahtamova*¹*Abstract:*

This article describes the category of person that has both inflectional and lexical aspects, and the distinction provides a finely graduated grammatical trait, relatively stable in both families and areas, and revealing for both typology and linguistic geography. Inflectional behavior includes reference to speech-act roles, indexation of arguments, discreteness from other categories such as number or gender, assignment and/or placement in syntax, arrangement in paradigms, and general resemblance to closed-class items.

Key words: person, inflection, morphology, linguistic geography, typology.

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1. Introduction

Person, probably more than any other inflectional category, originates in arguments but is strongly prone to end up as indexation on predicates and other phrase heads. As a result, person can be either lexical, figuring in independent arguments, or inflectional, figuring in indexation paradigms.

This distinction, surveyed over a number of grammatical contexts, can be used to form a fine-grained composite notion which answers the current need for more such typological variables for use in tracking incremental diachronic developments and gradual spatial distributions, and it can integrate local relationships with long-distance and long-term ones on a single scale. At the high inflectional end of the scale, person marking is similar to head marking, a coarse-grained variable with few settings and one which can represent transitions only as large leaps and can capture only relatively gross differences.

The first order of business in a discussion of lexical vs. inflectional person is to define person, inflection(al), and lexical, which is done in the next two subsections. A grammatical category or grammatical feature is a property of items within the grammar of a language. Within each category there are two or more possible values (sometimes called grammemes), which are normally mutually exclusive.

Grammatical Person

In linguistics, grammatical person is the grammatical distinction between deictic references to participant(s) in an event; typically, the distinction is between the speaker (first person), the addressee (second person), and others (third person). First person includes the speaker (English: I, we, me, and us), second person is the person or people spoken to (English: you), and third person includes all that are not listed above. Grammatical person typically defines a language's set of personal pronouns.

In Indo-European languages, first-, second-, and third-person pronouns are typically also marked for singular and plural forms, and sometimes dual form as well grammatical number. Some other languages use different classifying systems, especially in the plural pronouns. One frequently found difference not present in most Indo-European languages is

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a contrast between inclusive and exclusive 7 "we": a distinction of first-person plural pronouns between including or excluding the addressee [1,256]. Many languages express person with different morphemes in order to distinguish degrees of formality and informality. A simple honorific system common among European languages is the T-V distinction. Some other languages have much more elaborate systems of formality that go well beyond the T-V distinction, and use many different pronouns and verb forms that express the speaker's relationship with the people they are addressing.

In many languages, the verb takes a form dependent on the person of the subject and whether it is singular or plural. In English, this happens with the verb to be as follows [2, 465] • I am (first-person singular) • you are/thou art (second-person singular) • he, she, one, it is/they are (third-person singular) • we are (first-person plural) • you are/ye are (second-person plural) • they are (third-person plural) Other verbs in English take the suffix -s to mark the present tense third person singular, excluding singular 'they'

Additional Persons

The grammar of some languages divides the semantic space into more than three persons. The extra categories may be termed fourth person, fifth person, etc. Such terms are not absolute but can refer depending on context to any of several phenomena. The obviative is sometimes called the fourth person. The term fourth person is also sometimes used for the category of indefinite or generic referents, which work like one in English phrases such as "one should be prepared" or people in people say that..., when the grammar treats them differently from ordinary third-person forms The so called "zero person [4,213]. In English language constructions involving one, e.g. "One hopes that will not happen," are rare and could be considered expressive of an overly academic tone to the majority of people are recognizable to and used by young children in both languages.

Syntactic positioning.

Person markers are assigned and positioned in the syntax, chiefly by rules of agreement or indexation, which assign them to the head of a phrase or to a position relative to a head or to clause or phrase boundaries (clause-second, phrase-final, etc.). Assignment in the syntax distinguishes inflectional from derivational morphemes or categories [3,56], but I believe it also distinguishes inflectional from lexical categories. The choice of lexemes is a matter of semantics and lexicon, not syntax. At first glance it may appear that the positioning of words by word-order rules is a matter of syntax applying to lexemes, but in fact what is positioned by word-order rules is not lexemes but argument types or terms of syntactic relations.

Furthermore, word-order rules position them not relative to heads but to each other. Thus, inflectional morphemes, but not derivational morphemes or lexical ones (whether roots, stems, or words), are assigned and positioned in the syntax. Note also that inflectional person categories are properties of arguments but end up marked (e.g. indexed) on other words, usually heads, and there is nothing analogous to this in word order rules.

Conclusion

Person markers have a strong cross-linguistic tendency to occur in paradigms, and consequently they are prone to display properties of small closed sets such as a shared phonotactic canon, other phonological properties such as assonance (discussed below), portmanteau coding, deponence, and syncretism. Lexical person morphemes, in contrast, share essential properties with lexemes. The clearest examples of lexical person morphemes are independent pronouns, and these often share inflectional categories and/or inflectional classes with nouns. Their meanings often include not just locutor reference and not just

person but formality, social status, generation level, sex, and other categories that are more lexicosemantic than grammatical.

References:

- [1]. Abbi, Anvita. 2013. *A Grammar of the Great Andamanese Language. An Ethnolinguistic Study*. Leiden: Brill
- [2]. Arkadiev, P. M., Ju. A. Lander, A. B. Letučij, N.R. Sumbatova, and Ja. G. Testeleťs. 2009. *Vvedenie. Osnovnye svedenija ob adygejskom jazyke*. P. M. Arkad'ev, Ju.
- [3]. Bickel, Balthasar. 2011. *Grammatical relations typology*. In Jae Jung Song, ed., *The Oxford Handbook of Linguistic Typology*, 399-444. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [4]. Cysouw, Michael. 2003. *The Paradigmatic Structure of Person Marking*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [5]. Haspelmath, Martin and Andrea Sims. 2010. *Understanding Morphology*. London: Hodder Education.
- [6]. Hill, Kenneth C., ed. 1998. *Hopi Dictionary / Hopiikwa Lavaytutuveni: A Hopi-English Dictionary of the Third Mesa Dialect*. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- [7]. Kallio, Petri. 2015. *The language contact situation in prehistoric Northeastern Europe*. Robert Mailhammer, Theo Vennemann and Birgit Anette Olsen, eds., *The Linguistic Roots of Europe*, 77-102. Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanum Press, University of Copenhagen.
- [8]. Nichols, Johanna. 2016. *Noun-based and verb-based languages*. Poster, SLE Annual Meeting, Naples.
- [9]. Rood, David S., and Allan R. Taylor. 1996. *Sketch of Lakhota, a Siouan language*. In *Handbook of North American Indians*, vol. 17: *Languages*, ed. Ives Goddard. Washington: Smithsonian Institution.
- [10]. Shodiyev San'at E., "Деривационные особенности фразеологических выражений. Филологические науки. Т5-2019"
- [11]. Van Valin, Robert D., Jr. 1985. *Case marking and the study of the Lakhota clause*. In *Grammar Inside and Outside the Clause: Approaches to Theory from the Field*, ed. Johanna Nichols, and Anthony C. Woodbury. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- [12]. Watkins, Laurel J., and Parker McKenzie. 1984. *A Grammar of Kiowa*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press.
- [13]. Weber, David John. 1989. *A Grammar of Huallaga (Huanuco) Quechua*. Berkeley-Los Angeles: University of California Press.
- [14]. Witzlack-Makarevich, Alena. 2010. *Typological Variation in Grammatical Relations*. Ph.D. dissertation, University of Leipzig.